

APÊNDICE J – MAPPING BETWEEN THE MPO AND THE OBSERVATORY MODELS IDENTIFIED IN THE LITERATURE

The Table presents a mapping between MPO and the other models presented in works related to this thesis, with the purpose of identifying the specific concepts proposed in MPO that were covered (partially or totally) by the other models.

– Mapping between MPO and the observatory models identified in the literature

Concepts Intermediates	Concepts Specifics	Soares (2018)	Back (2016)	Yoshiura (2018)	Brown (2017)
Components	Collection	No	No	Cob (-)	Cob (+)
	Dissemination	No	No	No	Cob (+)
	Processing	No	No	Cob (+)	Cob (+)
	Storage	No	No	Cob (+)	Cob (+)
	Relationship	No	No	Cob (-)	Cob (+)
Contents	Projects	Cob (-)	Cob (-)	No	No
	Theme of Projects	No	Cob (-)	No	No
	Users	No	No	No	No
	Observatories	No	No	No	Cob (-)
Characteristics	Scope	No	No	No	No
	Access	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	collaboration network	Cob (-)	No	Cob (+)	Cob (+)
	Data Format	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	Sustainability	No	Cob (+)	Cob (-)	No
	Interoperability	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	Interactivity	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	Partial Data	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	Usability	No	No	No	No
	Security	No	No	Cob (+)	No
	Data Management	Cob (-)	No	Cob (+)	No

Quadro 29 – (continued)

Concepts Intermediates	Concepts Specifics	Soares (2018)	Back (2016)	Yoshiura (2018)	Brown (2017)
	Software	Cob (-)	No	Cob (+)	No
	Services	Cob (-)	No	No	No
	Redes	Cob (-)	No	No	No
	Hardware	Cob (-)	No	No	No
Manage Data and Information	Treat	Cob (+)	No	Cob (-)	Cob (+)
	Collect	Cob (-)	Cob (-)	Cob (-)	Cob (+)
	Store	Cob (-)	No	Cob (+)	Cob (+)
	Make available	No	No	No	Cob (+)
Produce Knowledge and Intelligence	Transform	Cob (+)	Cob (-)	Cob (+)	No
	Communicate	Cob (+)	Cob (+)	Cob (+)	No
	Categorize / Sort	No	No	No	No
	View	No	No	No	No
	Hold Responsible	No	No	No	No
	Interact	No	No	No	Cob (-)
	Track	Cob (-)	No	No	No
	Evaluate	No	No	No	No
	Match	No	No	No	Cob (-)
Collaborate	No	No	No	Cob (+)	
Actors cline2-6	Stakeholders of the Projects	No	Cob (-)	Cob (-)	Cob (-)
	Management Team and Development	Cob (-)	Cob (+)	Cob (+)	No
	Users of Observatory	Cob (+)	Cob (-)	Cob (+)	No
	Systems	No	No	Cob (+)	Cob (+)
	Transparency	No	No	No	No
	Decision Making	No	No	No	No
	Control	No	No	No	No

Quadro 29 – (continued)

Concepts Intermediates	Concepts Specifics	Soares (2018)	Back (2016)	Yoshiura (2018)	Brown (2017)
	Interaction	No	No	No	No
	Knowledge	No	No	No	No
	Learning	No	No	No	No
	Improvement	No	No	No	No
	Innovation	No	No	No	No
	Engagement	No	No	No	No
	Dissemination	No	No	No	No
	Prioritization	No	No	No	No

Source: author.